
ASSESSING FAÇADE-MOUNTED WINDCATCHER SUPPLY OUTLET HEIGHT'S INFLUENCE ON INDOOR AIR QUALITY IN RESIDENTIAL BEDROOMS

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Abstract.

The optimum location of a windcatcher supply outlet on the facade of a building in relation to the occupant breathing zone in the context of indoor air quality (IAQ) is imperative. This study attempts to determine the optimum location of the windcatcher supply outlet on the facade of a bedroom for enhanced IAQ. The building model was created using Design Builder software while computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was employed for the parametric simulation using air change effectiveness (ACE) as the optimization objective function. The height of the windcatcher supply outlet was varied from 0.2m to 2.4m step 0.2m above the floor level. The results show that higher values of ACE in the occupants' breathing zone were obtained at lower heights of the windcatcher supply outlets with the best ACE of 1.13 obtained at 0.4m. This information could help engineers to optimally position the windcatcher supply outlet on the façade of a bedroom building or any other building with similar attributes.

Keywords: Indoor air quality, bedroom building, windcatcher, rooftop, mean age of air, air change effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Buildings play a pivotal role in establishing a comfortable habitation milieu. Windcatchers, as passive systems, operate exclusively through natural ventilation modalities. The term "wind tower" or "windcatcher," as delineated by Mahsan *et al.* (2017), refers to a traditional method of natural ventilation, affixed either to the rooftop or façade of a structure, designed to harness swift air currents and channel them into the building's interior space. Windcatchers, an architectural convention of historical repute (Ionesco *et al.*, 2015; Abd Wahab *et al.*, 2018), operate autonomously, obviating the necessity for mechanical or electrical power inputs. These systems are deployable across a spectrum of architectural configurations and contribute substantially to the occupants' well-being, encompassing facets of air quality and thermal comfort.

Dwelling structures are conceived with a multiplicity of apertures including windows and vents, primarily aimed at fostering a healthful indoor milieu for inhabitants. Contrasting these apertures, windcatchers offer a suite of advantages surpassing conventional openings (Montazeri & Azizian, 2009; Abd Wahab *et al.*, 2019). In densely urbanized settings, windows often exhibit suboptimal efficiency, thereby positioning windcatchers as efficacious alternatives, adept at meeting requisite ventilation rates. Noteworthy research by Drach (2009) investigated a tri-level residence characterized by inadequate natural ventilation. The findings of this study substantiate the augmentation of natural airflow within the domicile through the incorporation of a windcatcher. In contrast to fenestral apertures, windcatchers boast a comparatively elevated pressure coefficient (Montazeri & Azizian, 2009). Their versatile utility extends to basement ventilation, ameliorating temperature fluctuations within enclosed spaces (Reyes, 2015).

Numerous research endeavors have been undertaken to elevate the performance, efficiency, and efficacy of windcatcher systems. In the study by Ghaemmaghami and Mahmoudi (2021), an investigation was carried out on windcatchers categorized into distinct blade configurations, namely x-blades, +blades, and H-blades. The findings unequivocally demonstrated that windcatchers equipped with H-blades exhibited superior performance. Montazeri (2011) delved into the functionality of windcatchers possessing a cylindrical cross-section and varying numbers of apertures. The outcomes unequivocally indicated that windcatchers with a dual-sided design exhibited the most optimal performance.

The research by Sheikhshahrokhdehkordi *et al.* (2020) delved into windcatcher variations of differing heights. The results gleaned from this study elucidated a direct correlation between heightened windcatcher structures and diminished mass flow rates. Afshin *et al.* (2014) conducted an exhaustive study involving a windcatcher-integrated building juxtaposed with neighboring structures of varying elevations. The outcomes of this inquiry underscored the influence of neighboring building height on ventilation rates, indicating that the presence of shorter buildings in proximity (with a height equivalent to 0.5H of the windcatcher and a distance of 0.75H from the windcatcher) amplifies ventilation rates, whereas taller neighboring structures exert a contrary effect.

Mak *et al.* (2005) conducted an in-depth investigation on the performance of a four-sided windcatcher across different wind angles—0°, 15°, 30°, and 45°. Particularly noteworthy were the findings that underscored heightened sensitivity of the windcatcher at a 45° wind angle, juxtaposed with diminished sensitivity to velocity changes at a 0° wind angle. Bahadori *et al.* (2008) conducted a comparative analysis of novel windcatcher designs against traditional

models. Wet column and wet surface windcatcher variants were introduced, demonstrating heightened performance compared to their conventional counterparts.

However, despite the substantial body of research aimed at enhancing windcatcher performance, a noticeable gap exists in the exploration of the optimal positioning of windcatcher supply air outlets on rooftops. This research void prompts the current study, which endeavors to optimize the positioning of windcatcher supply air outlets on rooftops, with the ultimate aim of enhancing indoor air quality within a centrally situated sleeper compartment.

RESEARCH EDIFICE

The examined structure constituted a bedroom measuring 4 meters in length, 3.5 meters in width, and 3 meters in height, situated within the confines of Sharada Industrial Estate in Kano, Nigeria. This particular room accommodated a solitary adult male occupant. A representative example of a windcatcher affixed to the façade is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A Typical Façade-Mounted Windcatcher

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed for this study highlighted step by step are presented hereunder.

Generation of Three-Dimensional Model for the Bedroom Structure

The dimensions of the bedroom building, measuring 4 meters in length, 3.5 meters in width, and 3 meters in height, were replicated within the DesignBuilder software. The spatial configuration of the bedroom model was visually depicted in Figure 2, elucidating the zone level arrangement.

Mesh Formation and Sensitivity Investigation

The establishment of computational grids and the evaluation of their self-sufficiency through meticulous examination are imperative for attaining an effective and precise solution. Extensive research underscores that an excessively coarse grid culminates in imprecise outcomes, whereas an overly refined grid yields accurate results but bears the burden of

escalated computational expenses and time consumption. The interplay between solution precision and expenditure is intrinsically intertwined with power quality. To generate the grid for the building model, a homogenous rectilinear coordinate system was employed. This grid was established employing default parameters conducive to a rudimentary mesh that aligns with the geometric configuration of a single-zone model, while adhering to fundamental mesh criteria. Notably, a default mesh interval of 0.300, a grid line connectivity tolerance of 0.0300, and a total of 2329 elements were employed, as illustrated in Figure 3(a).

In the pursuit of grid independence, three further iterations were developed, marked by increased refinement with element counts of 38038, 69904, and 276492. This enhancement was achieved by adjusting parameters such as "Max. X Size," "Max. Y Size," and "Max. Z Size." The augmented grids are depicted in Figure 3 (b, c, and d).

Figure 3: Coarse and refined meshes of the geometrical model

The Boundary Conditions

In this investigation, the delineation of boundary conditions encompasses two distinct categories: those applicable to external Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis, and those pertinent to internal CFD analysis. The boundary conditions pertinent to the internal CFD analysis encompass the following specifications: a windcatcher outlet airflow rate of 268 L/s, accompanied by a temperature of 24°C; the southern window is characterized by an

airflow rate of 72 L/s and a temperature of 28.2°C; fixed heat flux values of 0.299 kW and 0.198 kW are respectively assigned to the eastern and southern walls; the remaining walls, ceiling, and floor are treated as isenthalpic boundaries; the enclosed space accommodates one occupant, generating a fixed heat flux of 7.97 W/m²; the presence of a laptop introduces an additional fixed heat flux of 3.37 W/m²; human metabolic activity is characterized by 1.0 met (58.2 W/m²), and clothing insulation is set at 0.5 clo (0.08 °C·m²/W); the zone's air temperature is established at 31.3°C, accompanied by a relative humidity of 60%; the calculation of mean radiant temperature involves 24 sphere segments.

Regarding external boundary conditions, the following attributes are specified: a grid spacing of 2.0000 meters; a grid merge tolerance of 0.2000 meters; a prevailing wind velocity of 3.24 m/s, originating from the southern direction; the exposure classification is defined as suburban; site domain dimensions encompass a length of 3.00 meters, a width of 3.00 meters, and a height of 1.40 meters.

Model validation

Subsequent to achieving grid independence, the fidelity of the model was ascertained through a comprehensive validation protocol. The validation endeavor entailed a meticulous correspondence analysis between the empirically observed temperature readings within the bedroom study area, outfitted with the windcatcher, and the computationally simulated internal temperature derived from the CFD model. The comparative assessment between experimental and simulated interior temperatures is visually represented in Figure 4, serving as a tangible manifestation of the validation process.

Figure 4: Comparison between Simulated versus Measured Temperatures

At a 95% confidence level, the coefficient of correlation between the observed and computationally simulated temperatures stands at 0.914. This robust correlation underscores the elevated precision of the employed building model within the ambit of this investigation.

Determination of Air Change Effectiveness

The utilization of DesignBuilder software facilitated the delineation of the respiratory space around the slumbering occupant. The software's operational framework entails the

computation of Air Change Effectiveness (ACE) by amalgamating the designated 'breathing region' with the purpose of delineating the portions of the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) domain relevant for ACE calculations. These regions were incorporated through the specification of the origin's coordinates and the region's dimensions. In accordance with the principles set forth by ASHRAE Standard-62.1 (2007) for breathing zone delineations, this study adhered to the specifications outlined in Table 1, encapsulating the coordinates of the origin and the dimensions of the breathing zone.

Table 1: Breathing Zone of the Occupied Space

Coordinate of Origin		Dimensions(m)	
X	10.884	Length	1.644
Y	11.602	Width	1.580
Z	0.862	Height	0.78

Parametric analysis of the CFD model

The DesignBuilder software facilitated a parametric analysis, whereby the boundary conditions were maintained at a consistent level while systematically altering the windcatcher supply outlet position in increments of 0.2 meters, ranging from 0.2 meters to 2.4 meters above the floor level. Subsequently, DesignBuilder's Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation was executed to elucidate the influence of the windcatcher supply outlet positioning on Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), gauged by the Air Change Effectiveness (ACE) serving as the metric for evaluating performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The depicted numerical outcomes in Figure 5 illustrate the variations in Air Change Effectiveness (ACE) pertaining to the bedroom structure integrated with the windcatcher. These variations are based on the alteration of the supply outlet's height, ranging from 0.2 meters to 2.4 meters in increments of 0.2 meters.

Figure 5: ACE vs Height of Windcatcher Supply Outlet above Floor Level

The results of the parametric simulations of the ACE in the occupants' breathing zone of the bedroom building with the height of the windcatcher supply outlets varying from 0.2m to 2.4m step 0.2m as shown in Fig. 5. It can be seen that higher values of ACE were 1.04, 1.13, and 1.02 which were obtained at windcatcher supply outlet heights of 0.2m, 0.4m, and 0.6m from floor level respectively, with the highest value of ACE obtained at 0.4m height. This finding might be attributed to the windcatcher behaving purely as a displacement ventilation system. The thermal plumes created by the heat sources such as the occupants and electric appliances allows the freshly cooled air to displace the warmer stale air above occupants breathing zone. This finding is in consonance with the works of Ameen *et al.* (2019) and Tian *et al.* (2020) who stated that in a displacement ventilation system, the values of ACE are higher primarily due to the displacement of contaminated air above the occupants' breathing zone.

For a perfectly mixed ventilation, the ACE is 1.0 (ASHRAE-62.1, 2016). Therefore, from Fig. 5, it can be seen that at the windcatcher supply outlet heights of 0.4m, 0.5m, and 0.6m, the values of ACE were greater 1.0 which indicates that at these heights, the windcatcher supplied freshly cooled air directly into the occupants' breathing zone. This finding is in consonance with the work of Sinha *et al.* (2000) who concluded that the best location for enhancing the ACE in a space is by placing the diffuser of the ventilation system closer to the floor. From Fig. 5, it can also be seen that lower values of ACE were obtained at relatively higher windcatcher supply heights above the floor level. This might be attributed to the fact that at higher windcatcher supply heights, the freshly cooled air supplied by the windcatcher falls into the rising warmer stale air thereby diluting it. When this happens, the quality of air in the breathing zone of the occupants would be lowered. That is why the ACE at higher supply outlets are less than unity. This finding agreed with the work of Lee *et al.* (2007) who experimentally compared high wall jet from grill diffusers with typical ceiling diffusers and concluded that the ceiling diffusers are better in terms of air change effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

A numerical inquiry was conducted to explore the impact of the windcatcher supply outlet's height on the Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) within a windcatcher-equipped bedroom building. Notably, it was observed that lower supply outlet heights yielded improved Air Change Effectiveness (ACE) within the occupants' breathing zone. The optimal outcome was recorded at a supply outlet height of 0.4 meters above the floor level. Consequently, within bedroom structures outfitted with windcatchers, the attainment of enhanced IAQ is attainable through the adoption of lower supply outlet heights. These insights hold practical implications for architects and engineers, to guide them in the strategic positioning of windcatcher supply outlets to optimize IAQ within bedroom structures or analogous building configurations.

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